

1 **Metabolic changes during resistance to chemotherapy in TNBC cells *in vitro*.**

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7 We describe changes in metabolic gene expression in TNBC cells in response to exposure to
8 chemotherapeutic agents *in vitro*. Malic acid biosynthesis enzyme *ME3* was silenced. *PHGDH* was
9 activated. Aldolase was induced, as was *PFKFB2*.

10 Citations

11 1. Dey, P., Baddour, J., Muller, F., Wu, C.C., Wang, H., Liao, W.T., Lan, Z., Chen, A., Gutschner, T.,
12 Kang, Y. and Fleming, J., 2017. Genomic deletion of malic enzyme 2 confers collateral lethality in
13 pancreatic cancer. *Nature*, 542(7639), pp.119-123.